

Telefonica

Open Source
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5G Verticals Session

*How can OSM accelerate
5G Vertical Services?*

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#RECONNECTA

5GINFIRE

Disclaimer!

Telcos & Verticals have evolved differently...

... and language is a key divergence

Telcos

- Reference Architecture
- Network Topology
- 5G frequencies
- Network KPIs
- Revenue

Verticals

- What do I have to install?
- How do I connect things?
- As long as it is not Wi-Fi...
- Application KPIs
- Zero evaluation cost

About Reference Architectures: quick poll

How many of you work for a Vertical?

Please, take a look at the Figure
With the mindset of a Vertical...

How many of you find this Reference Architecture useful for your business?

Source: Microsoft Cybersecurity Reference Architecture

Predicted results*

* No offense intended to owner of Reference Architecture; this invented exercise is just for concept illustration purposes

About 5G KPIs

OSM and telco operators

Some of these can be derived from
**IMPROVED SERVICE DEPLOYMENT
CAPABILITIES**

OSM and telco operators (cont.)

**INTEREST BY OPERATORS IN
MANO IMPLEMENTATIONS,
LIKE OSM**

What about Verticals?

AUTOMOTIVE INDUSTRY

Main trends

5G

Edge Computing

How can OSM accelerate 5G Vertical Services?

AUTOMOTIVE INDUSTRY

5G

NEW SERVICE!

Main phases

Complexity of testing by Verticals

Experiments Heterogeneity

- Each Vertical its own Use Cases
- Reusable VNFs? Fake VNFs?
- No lab fits all

Vertical/Facility Interaction

- Do they speak the same language?
- What testing services are offered?
- How do I use them?

5G Testing Scenarios

- Very specialized (equipment cost)
- Regionally distributed
- Very occupied

Testing Methodology

- Is it secure?
- Does it have an impact in the rest of the infrastructure?
- Is it standard?

Validation of results

- Can I measure the required KPIs?
- Assurance of appropriate conditions (i.e. close to production conditions)
- Can I replicate my tests?

Few comments on few topics...

Experiments Heterogeneity

- Each Vertical its own Use Cases
- **Reusable VNFs?** Fake VNFs?
- No lab fits all

Vertical/Facility Interaction

- **Do they speak the same language?**
- What test cases are offered?
- How to integrate them?

DESCRIPTORS

5G Testing Scenarios

- Very specialized (equipment cost)
- **Regionally distributed**
- Very occupied

Testing Methodology

- Is it secure?
- **Does it have any impact on the rest of the network structure?**
- Is it standard?

SLICES

Validation of results

- Can I measure the required KPIs?
- Assurance of appropriate conditions (i.e. close to production conditions)
- **Can I replicate my tests?**

The OSM example

LOCAL DEVELOPMENT & TESTING

TEST POOL FOR DEVELOPERS

SERVICE PROVIDER

- ✓ Open development environment
- ✓ Functional testing
- ✓ Low cost
- ✓ Integration from the beginning

- ✓ Real servers and switches
- ✓ Performance tests (EPA can be enforced)
- ✓ Cost effective shared infrastructure
- ✓ Move the value to VNF services

- ✓ Production/pre-production environment
- ✓ Real network scenarios
- ✓ Final service configuration
- ✓ Fast deployment
- ✓ Low final integration cost

SAME **IMAGES** AND **VNF PACKAGE** ACROSS ALL THE CHAIN!

REPLICATION
OF TESTS

REPLICATION OF OSM?

**OPEN DISCUSSION:
PLEASE, ASK
AND CONTRIBUTE**

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